

Health monitoring for electro mechanical actuators from design to operation

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Abstract

Nowadays, large aeronautical multinationals, aircraft Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) and their suppliers are immersed in the concept called "More Electric Aircraft", which will enable the aircraft industry to improve significantly in terms of reduction in aircraft weight, fuel consumption, total life cycle costs, maintainability and reliability. This trend is accelerating in recent years and these companies are investing heavily towards this concept of more electric aircraft, in which traditional hydraulic and pneumatic systems are being replaced by electrically-driven systems [1].

"All-electric" aircraft [2] means that all power off-takes from the aircraft are electrical in nature, thus removing the need for on-engine hydraulic power generation and bleed air off-takes. Removal of the engine hydraulic pumps requires fully-operative electrical power actuators.

EMA technologies are already being used in aeronautics, but for safety reasons they are limited to Secondary Flight Controls or military aircraft[3]. Their application to Primary Flight Controls will allow reductions in the weight of drives, gas consumption, and polluting emissions. The major step in moving from EHAs to jam-free EMAs is the prevention of potential jamming cases by appropriate technology and monitoring, thus giving the system aircraft availability for dispatch and failure sizing cases.

Including more electronics in the actuators, it is also possible to predict how long an actuator will last, introducing the predictive maintenance instead of preventive maintenance today used by airlines.

This is the reason why health monitoring plays a mayor roll in the development of EMA's. It must be taken into account from the design phase on to the development and deployment phase.

In the present paper, a test bench for EMA's is presented, with a proposal of health monitoring. Different signals, concerning internal signals from the control and others such as acoustic emissions, accelerometers and motor current signature analysis, are analyzed and the result is shown.

Keywords: Health monitoring, Electro mechanical actuator, Aviation

INTRODUCTION

The "all-electric" aircraft is not a new concept: the concept of an electric aircraft has been considered by military aircraft designers since World War II [4], although until recently the technical complexity rendered the approach unfeasible; especially for commercial and civil transport applications.

Nowadays several systems work using energy directly from the jet motor [5]. In a mid-size aircraft the propulsion thrust is about 40 MW, in the case of the "non-thrust" power we have gearbox driven generators (for the electrical system) which take about 200 kW, high pressure air "bled" from engine (for the pneumatic system) which take about 1.2 MW, gearbox driven hydraulic pump (for the hydraulic system) which take about 240 kW and fuel pumps and oil pumps on engine (the mechanical system) which take about 100 kW, making a total "non-thrust" power of about 1.7 MW. By making all of these systems electric (removing pneumatic, hydraulic and mechanical networks) the total "non-thrust" power can be reduced to about 1MW.

Figure 1: Actual configuration of several systems on the "conventional" aircraft adapted from [5].

In this context, the development and the implementation of advanced actuation systems has increased, as many factors are driving the migration from hydraulic actuators to electro-mechanical actuators (EMAs). EMAs provide significant advantages in complex applications because they increase the controllability of the system (shortening changeover times), provide re-configurability, maintain functionality during faults (improving the accuracy and reliability), and make it possible to carry out advanced diagnostics and prognostics for a more intelligent maintenance, furthering the increment of the aircraft availability with the long-term planning for maintenance activities. Overall, the main objective for the companies in the last few years is to save operating costs, fuel burn and environmental impact.

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A successful health and usage monitoring system (HUMS) should be able to diagnose and report the nature of the fault. Providing the means for prediction of remaining useful life and the preventing mayor faults.

Additional advantages concern redundant equipment. In current systems, general flight controls are usually implemented by fault tolerant centralized redundant systems, which are built up by complex and expensive Central Power Units. The new distributed EMA architectures allow us to work on a completely different basis by enabling the isolation of any faulty equipment from the full actuator network by means of a simple switch.

For the first time in aeronautics history [2], the “more electric aircraft” approach may dramatically reduce or eliminate the need for centralized aircraft hydraulic power systems and replace them with an electrical power system with greatly improved reliability, and maintenance and support potential, as well as the possibility for significant improvements in terms of weight, volume, and system complexity.

Before the step of inserting the actuators in aircrafts, extensive tests in ground must be performed. With this objective, IK4-Tekniker with the help of Liebherr-Aerospace Lindenberg GmbH, a test bench for electro mechanical actuators has been developed.

GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE TEST BENCH FOR EMA TESTING

Figure 2: General view of the test bench.

In figure above a general view of the test bench is shown. The electromechanical actuator confronts a hydraulic actuator that provides the load. The actuator is set at 32 °, mimicking the position for primary flight control units. The load is generated by the hydraulic system. It mimics the loads that the actuator will meet in flight.

The test bench is fitted with security elements preventing the overrun and overcharge of the electro-mechanical actuator.

There is a control unit for the actuator and the hydraulic system, and an acquisition unit, based on products from National instruments. For the health monitoring a selection of sensors was made. The objective is to have the main sources of information to determine the health state of the actuator, and to be able to monitor its evolution.

Sensors for health and usage monitoring

A HUMS for a primary flight surface control unit EMAs should be composed by these main modules:

- Measurement related to efficiency of system.
- Cycle counter
- Health Monitoring: Signals from sensors.
- Life estimators depending on actuator status.

To fulfill the needs linked with the cycle counter the systems relies in the monitoring of internal signals. The different parameters of the test are saved.

- Number of cycles
- Time working
- Speed
- Position

For the health monitoring and the life estimation sensors have been added to the actuator.

Temperature. Room temperature and the temperature in different sensible positions of the EMA.

Accelerometer: a 3-axis accelerometer has been installed in the test bench. high frequency triaxial accelerometer properly allocated in the test rig (CTC, AC230-2D/006M-F3C) [6]. This model had a measuring range from 0.6 Hz to 10 KHz, enough to cover the entire frequency spectrum to be measured in the test rig.

Figure 3: CTC AC 230 tri-axial accelerometer.

Acoustic emission: An acoustic emission sensor has been installed in the test bench. The sensor selected is a 8152C0050000 from Kistler [7]. The frequency range of measurement is: 50 KHz and 400 KHz.

Figure 4: KISTLER 8152C0050000 sensor.

Motor current signature analysis: The current that the motor consumes is monitored with a sensor LEM HTA 100S [8] sensor installed in the electric cabinet.

Figure 5: LEM HTA sensor.

CONCLUSIONS

A test rig for the testing of electro mechanical actuators for aeronautical use has been designed and built. The health and usage of the electro mechanical actuator is tested and measured, giving rise to the possibility of performing life predictions.

SUMMARY

Electro mechanical actuators present the future of aviation as they offer several advantages. Among those is the possibility of doing health monitoring. Under the Clean Sky project ISSELUB a test bench for EMA's has been developed, with the insertion of several sensors for the measurement of the performance and the health state.

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